

P26 Good Research Practice

Purpose

This policy applies to all stages of research from design through to dissemination.

In this policy, research is defined as a process of investigation leading to new insights, effectively shared. This includes but is not limited to clinical, computational, and laboratory research as well as qualitative approaches such as surveys and focus groups.

This policy has been designed to encourage good conduct in research so as to maximise the benefits of research for: researchers, patients, and the broader public. In conjunction with HDR UK's related policies, this policy promotes a research and innovation culture defined by integrity, good governance and best practice.

This policy has been developed in accordance with external standards and guidance including:

- [The Declaration on Research Assessment](#)
- [Coalition for Advancing Research Assessment: COARA](#)
- [Concordat on Open Research Data](#)
- [Technician Commitment](#)
- [The Goldacre Report](#)
- [Concordat to Support Research Integrity](#)
- [Concordat for Engaging the Public with Research](#)
- [Concordat to Support the Career Development of Researchers](#)
- [Concordat on Openness in Animal Research](#)
- [UKRI Embedding Diversity in Research Design](#)

Responsibility

All Staff, Secondees, and Community Members¹ are responsible for ensuring that all research is conducted in accordance with this policy.

Programme directors, team leaders, and/or managers are responsible for their team's awareness and compliance with this policy.

¹ Any individuals in receipt of funding from HDR UK or involved in an HDR UK programme or project including Institute Research Organisation Directors, Associate Directors, Researchers, Scientists, Technologists, Triallists, Fellows and Post Doctoral Researchers, PhD and MSc students

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Summary

This overarching policy contains elements relating to good practice in research across the research lifecycle, organised as follows:

- [Research Design and Methodology](#)
- [FAIR and Open Data](#)
- [Open Access](#)
- [Research Involving Animals](#)
- [Research Misuse/Bioterrorism](#)
- [Research Culture and the Career Development of Researchers](#)

The detail herein outlines HDR UK's research **requirements, expectations and encouragement of good practices**.

Research Design and Methodology

HDR UK advocates good practice in research design and methodology to improve research quality, facilitate reproducibility, and increase patient and public trust in science.

Principles

Ethics and Governance

- All researchers are expected to be up-to-date with the national, institutional, and funder policies that apply to their research.
- Studies involving human participants (including personal data or samples) require a research ethics committee (REC) review; for Community Members, this is usually sought from the lead researcher's university or from one of the Health Research Authority's (HRA) NHS RECs. Noting that NHS REC review is a requirement for certain types of research.
- Research conducted by or led by Staff or Secondes may need both scientific and NHS REC or other ethical review. For research not subject to external review, HDR UK will conduct a proportionate risk and ethics review.
- Data access approval(s) must be sought, where needed, to ensure required data governance standards are met.
- To ensure both scientific and ethical robustness, all research projects, including surveys of patients, public or other stakeholders, should only be conducted by appropriately trained Staff or Secondes (e.g., appropriate knowledge and expertise in questionnaire design and use of online survey tools is required before designing and undertaking a survey).

- Researchers collecting data must also have participants' consent to collect, use, store and share their personal data.
- The confidentiality and rights of research participants and the security of datasets must be protected following the principles and procedures of [Five Safes Framework](#).
- Research which involves health and social care must adhere to the principles and good practises set out in the [UK Policy Framework for Health and Social Care Ethics](#).
- Research undertaken in global, low resource settings must uphold the [principles set out for the HDR Global programme](#), which are based on those developed for the International COVID-19 Data Alliance (ICODA) initiative.
- Where possible, research studies should be pre-registered in a publicly accessible database; clinical trials must be prospectively registered at [ClinicalTrials.gov](#), [ISRCTN registry](#), and/or another registry listed on the [WHO International Clinical Trials Registry Platform \(ICTRP\)](#).
- Pre-registration should include thorough details of the research protocol and planned statistical analyses to allow reproduction by an independent statistician; or this information should be provided in a separate, publicly available, protocol, including a statistical analysis plan.
- The adoption of Registered Reports, via open access venues, are encouraged.

Public and Patient Involvement and Engagement

- Public and patients must be actively involved in research with the aim of improving the quality and relevance of research, as well as serving the broader democratic principles of citizenship, accountability and transparency.
- Research must meet the [UK Standards for Public Involvement](#) and follow the [Guiding Principles](#) set out by HDR UK alongside the [Good Practice Standards for Public Engagement in Data for Research and Statistics](#) developed by PEDRI.

Diversity and Inclusion

- Diversity and inclusion must be considered by researchers when designing their research proposals, recruiting participants, and/or conducting research involving human participants, animals, their data or samples, including development of PPIE activities to support research design and conduct in accordance with the [UKRI Embedding Diversity in Research Design policy](#).
- A broad view of diversity and inclusion should be embedded into research design and methodology with the aim of reducing bias and exacerbation of health inequalities.
- Where collecting data about people's ethnicity, analysing differences between ethnic groups and/or publishing ethnicity data, researchers are encouraged to follow the [Standards for Ethnicity Data](#).
- Limitations and potential biases within data should be understood, recorded, and reported; where applicable, research should adopt the [SAGER guidelines](#), and [STANDING Together recommendations](#) for healthcare dataset standards supporting diversity, inclusivity, and generalisability.

Data Collection, Curation, Analyses, and Retention

- Care must be taken to determine and document the appropriate methodological and statistical approaches – and to identify and manage bias in data collection and analyses.
- Data must be actively managed throughout the research lifecycle; Data Management Plans (DMPs) should be developed to guide the responsible collection, formatting, preservation and sharing of data – as aligned with this policy.
- The use of Trusted Research Environments/Secure Data Environments is strongly encouraged, where available, for research involving sensitive data.
- Analytical work should adopt [Reproducible Analytical Pipeline baseline practices](#) (including code review) whilst striving for Silver and Gold, as developed by the RAP Community of Practice.
- Data Management scripts, analysis scripts and software should adhere to the [P17 Software Development and Training of AI Algorithms](#) policy.
- Well-described open standards for (meta)data should be adopted, where possible; for health-related data, where a specific data standard/model has not been adopted, use of the OMOP data model, SNOMED CT vocabulary, and HL7 FHIRv4 messaging specification standard is encouraged.
- Data must be stored with appropriate safeguards to protect individuals, and in accordance with organisational operating procedures and policies.
- The retention period for research data may be determined by law. Where it is not, Staff and Secondes acting in their HDR UK capacity should follow the guidance in [the MRC's Retention Framework for Research Data and Records](#). It is noted, however, that HDR UK collects and holds only very small quantities of research data, for example from surveys. Where HDR UK scientific staff access and work with personal health-related data, this is almost always within a Trusted Research Environment/Secure Data Environment hosted by a third party (e.g. SAIL Wales, NHS England, Public Health Scotland) and data retention policies will be those of the relevant organisation. Community Members should adhere to best data retention practices set out by their organisation.

Reporting Guidelines

Research must comply with consensus-based minimum reporting guidelines including:

- Clinical trial protocols ([SPIRIT](#))
- Clinical trial protocols evaluating interventions with an AI component ([SPIRIT-AI](#))
- Clinical trials ([CONSORT; MHRA Guidance](#))
- Clinical trials evaluating interventions with an artificial intelligence (AI) component ([CONSORT-AI](#))
- Diagnostic and prognostic studies ([STARD; TRIPOD](#))
- Clinical practice ([AGREE; RIGHT](#))
- Case Reports ([CARE](#))

- Patient and Public Involvement in Health and Social Care Research ([GRIPP 2](#))
- Observational studies ([STROBE](#), [RECORD](#))
- Qualitative research ([COREQ](#); [SRQR](#))
- Survey studies ([CROSS](#))

FAIR and Open Data

HDR UK endorses the [FAIR Data Principles](#) and [FAIR Principles for Research Software](#), alongside data and code sharing, as a framework to promote reproducibility and the broadest reuse of research.

HDR UK is committed to open licensing of research-related intellectual property. Written approval from HDR UK must be obtained prior to any registration or commercialisation of intellectual property where it was developed as part of an HDR UK programme or was funded (or partially funded) by HDR UK.

Principles

Data

- Data must be made available with as few restrictions as possible (i.e. '[as open as possible, as closed as necessary](#)') so as to maximise the value of the data for research and patient and public benefit; there may be cases where openly sharing data may not be feasible (due to ethical, data protection or confidentiality considerations), or because the data have been obtained from a third party and access restrictions apply.
- Data necessary to understand and validate published findings (or other types of research output) must be shared no later than the time of publication. As per [UKRI's Draft Research Data Policy](#), a limited period of exclusive use of data collected and analysed is reasonable in recognition of researchers' intellectual contribution and for the research team to have first opportunity to publish or otherwise exploit the results of their research. Any period of exclusive use must be balanced against the public interest in releasing data, considering the wider value of the data, research methodology, and domain-specific standards and best practice.
- Where it is safe, legal, and ethical to do so, data should be hosted in a stable, community-recognised repository under a CC BY or CC 0 licence and assigned a globally unique persistent identifier (PID, such as a DOI).
- Where data cannot be shared, metadata record(s) should be made openly available in relevant catalogues (if health data related, metadata should be stored in the Health Data Research Gateway).
- Appropriate metadata and additional documentation must be made available alongside data to ensure understanding and reuse.
- Data custodians and data holding organisations are encouraged to follow [the Alliance Principles for Participation](#) and adopt the use of Data Registers.

Trusted Research Environments (TRE) / Secure Data Environments (SDE)

- All research must comply with the policies and procedures set out by the Trusted Research Environments/Secure Data Environments in which it is carried out including e.g. policies for [SAIL Databank](#), [Safe Havens in Scotland](#), and [NHS England](#).
- HDR UK recognises that sharing outputs such as aggregated or anonymised data from a Trusted Research Environment/Secure Data Environments will vary across providers and may be subject to approval processes and disclosure control rules.
- Any outputs exported from a Trusted Research Environment/Secure Data Environment should go through an output review process to ensure non-disclosure; for example, employing the [Output Review Process](#) as developed by the International COVID-19 Data Alliance (ICODA) initiative.
- Where data is accessed via a Trusted Research Environment/Secure Data Environment or provided by another party (such as the NHS), sharing must only proceed where there is an appropriate agreement.
- Researchers should undertake appropriate researcher accreditation e.g. an ONS Accredited Researcher.

Other Outputs

- Expectations and guidance for software sharing (including algorithms, code and workflows) are outlined in the [P17 Software Development and Training of AI algorithms](#) policy.
- Staff and Secondes must openly share other outputs arising from research. These may include, but are not limited to, case studies, white papers, technical reports, and survey findings. Provided it is safe, legal and ethical to do so, these outputs should be hosted in the [HDR UK Community Space on Zenodo](#) (or an appropriate community-recognised repository) under a CC BY licence and assigned a globally unique persistent identifier (PID, such as a DOI). To improve discoverability, links to such outputs should also be added to the Health Data Research Gateway, where appropriate.
- Secondes and Community Members are encouraged to openly share outputs for the benefit of all and are welcome to use the [HDR UK Community Space on Zenodo](#).

Open Access

HDR UK expects all findings from research it supports to be openly available, including peer-reviewed publications. Sharing outputs openly promotes reuse, delivers value for public money, and allows patients and the wider public to become more equal and informed research partners.

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Principles

- All outputs published in a peer-reviewed journal and supported in whole or in part by HDR UK funding, must be made immediately open access (via ‘green’ or ‘gold’ routes) under a CC BY license; an Open Government License may be used where the output is subject to crown copyright.
- Outputs should be made available through [Europe PMC](#) at the time of publication and ideally also added to the Health Data Research Gateway (linking to the relevant datasets and data analysis scripts or software used by the research project). In the Gateway, a publication can be either about a dataset (when describing a cohort) or using a dataset.
- Those in receipt of HDR UK funds may use their funding to pay an open access fee (e.g. article processing charges, where appropriate, to meet these principles). Note that the use of HDR UK funds for publishing in a ‘hybrid’ journal that is not part of a transitional agreement is not permitted.
- Outputs published in peer-reviewed journal articles must include a Data Access Statement, even where there are no data associated with the article or the data are inaccessible.
- Use of the Health Data Research Gateway should be attributed in a Data Access Statement as follows, noting this statement is in addition to, and does not replace, any other acknowledgements required by the data custodian:
- ‘Data discovery and access was facilitated by the Health Data Research Gateway- <https://www.healthdatagateway.org/> YEAR.’
- Where applicable, outputs published in peer-reviewed journal articles should include a Software Availability Statement detailing any code created for data management and analysis including: a link to the version-controlled source code, a link to a permanently archived version of the code, and the license under which the code may be reused. This link can also be added to the Gateway within “Analysis Scripts and Software” and associated with the datasets it can be applied to along with relevant associated publications.
- The publication of preprints via recognised preprint servers is actively encouraged; preprints should be linked to and/or cited in the final peer-reviewed output.
- All contributors (including: patients, data custodians, researchers, HDR UK, funders, etc) must be appropriately acknowledged in-line with [P28 Attribution Policy](#).
- Author contributions should be captured using the [CRediT taxonomy](#); special care should be taken where applicable to include investigators located at institutions in Low and Middle Income Countries (LMICs) that led original study implementation.
- Engagement with open peer review models is encouraged to support transparency and integrity.

Research Involving Animals

Whilst HDR UK does not directly support any research involving animals, the Institute expects that animal research is conducted in accordance with UK law and ethically approved by an independent review board. Animal research must follow the highest standards of [animal welfare](#) and adhere to the principles of the [Concordat on Openness in Animal Research](#). Every effort should be made to use technologies and approaches that refine, reduce, or replace the use of animal in research (as per the [National Centre for the 3Rs](#))

Research Misuse/Bioterrorism

HDR UK expects researchers to actively consider any potential risks of research outputs (including algorithms) being misused to cause harm both in the short and longer-term, when planning and conducting their research. This includes, but is not limited to, risks to: research participants, quality of care, and wider society.

Research Culture and the Career Development of Researchers

HDR UK recognises that behaviours and attitudes across individual, discipline, and institute levels are shaped by how success is defined, as well as whom and what is valued – and this, in turn, influences the way that research is conducted and communicated, and the career-paths of those people who participate.

HDR UK expects members from across its communities to work together to promote a more collaborative, supportive, and inclusive research culture.

Principles

- Research must comply with this policy alongside HDR UK’s policies on [P28 Attribution](#), [P25 Intellectual Property](#), and [P27 Research Integrity and Misconduct](#).
- Research assessment should be inclusive and recognise the range of research, roles, and cultures that enable impact.
- Clear career pathways in research should be developed and supported.
- Staff, Secondes, Community Members, and institute-partners, should be familiar with and champion the principles, as they apply, of:
 - [The Declaration on Research Assessment](#)
 - [Coalition for Advancing Research Assessment: COARA](#)
 - [Technician Commitment](#)

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- [Concordat to Support Research Integrity](#)
- [Concordat to Support the Career Development of Researchers](#)

Glossary

This glossary benefits from definitions provided by the Framework for Open and Reproducible Research Training ([Parsons et al 2022](#)).

Research: A process of investigation leading to new insights, effectively shared; this definition is taken from the UK's Research Excellence Framework.

Reproducibility: A minimum standard on a spectrum of activities ("reproducibility spectrum") for assessing the value or accuracy of scientific claims based on the original methods, data, and code.

Pre-registration: The practice of publishing the plan for a study, including research questions/hypotheses, research design, data analysis before the data has been collected or examined.

Registered Report: A scientific publishing format that includes an initial round of peer review of the background and methods (study design, measurement, and analysis plan); sufficiently high quality manuscripts are accepted for in-principle acceptance (IPA) at this stage.

5 safes: A set of principles which enable data services to provide safe research access to data.

Research Ethics Committee: A group of people appointed to review research proposals to assess formally if the research is ethical.

Public and Patient Involvement and Engagement: Working with patients and the public to shape research, and engage with it such that research is carried out 'with' or 'by' members of the public rather than 'to', 'about' or 'for' them.

Research Data Management: A broad concept that includes processes undertaken to create organized, documented, accessible, and reusable quality research data.

Data Management Plan: A structured document that describes the process of data acquisition, analysis, management and storage during a research project. It also describes data ownership and how the data will be preserved and shared during and upon completion of a project.

Data Use Register: Also known as a data release register or list of approved projects offers the public a clear record of how their data is being used, by whom and, most importantly, for what purpose.

Trusted Research Environment: Also known as Secure Data Environments, a secure computing environment that enables access to sensitive data for analyses.

Reproducible Analytical Pipeline: Automated statistical and analytical processes. They incorporate elements of software engineering best practice to ensure that the pipelines are reproducible, auditable, efficient, and high quality.

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Code Review: The process of checking another researcher’s programming (specifically, computer source code) including but not limited to statistical code and data modelling.

Persistent Identifier: A unique long-lasting reference to digital objects. An example of a persistent identifier is a DOI (digital object identifier) which is an alpha-numeric strings that can be assigned to any entity.

Creative Commons Licenses: A set of free and easy-to-use copyright licences that define the rights of the authors and users of open data and materials in a standardized way.

Synthetic data: Artificial data that is generated from original data and a model that is trained to reproduce the characteristics and structure of the original data.

Metadata: Structured data that describes and synthesises other data. Metadata can help find, organize, and understand data. Examples of metadata include creator, title, contributors, keywords, tags, as well as any kind of information necessary to verify and understand the results and conclusions of a study such as codebook on data labels, descriptions, the sample and data collection process.

FAIR Principles: Describes making outputs Findable, Accessible, Interoperable and Reusable (FAIR). ‘Findable’ and ‘Accessible’ are concerned with where materials are stored (e.g. in data repositories), while ‘Interoperable’ and ‘Reusable’ focus on the importance of data formats and how such formats might change in the future ([Wilkinson et al 2016](#)). The FAIR principles have been further adapted for computational workflows ([Goble et al 2020](#)) and software ([Chue Hong et al 2022](#)).

Workflows: Complex multi-step methods that are used for data collection, data preparation, analytics, predictive modelling, and simulation that lead to new data products.

Open Data: Data that is freely available and readily accessible for use by others without restriction.

Open Code: Making computer code (e.g., programming, analysis code, stimuli generation) freely and publicly available in order to make research methodology and analysis transparent and allow for reproducibility and collaboration.

Open Source Software: A type of computer software in which source code is released under a license that permits others to use, change, and distribute the software to anyone and for any purpose.

Open Science: An umbrella term reflecting the idea that scientific knowledge of all kinds, where appropriate, should be openly accessible, transparent, rigorous, reproducible, replicable, accumulative, and inclusive, all which are considered fundamental features of the scientific endeavour.

Open Access: “Free availability of scholarship on the public internet, permitting any users to read, download, copy, distribute, print, search, or link to the full texts of these research articles, crawl them for indexing, pass them as data to software, or use them for any other lawful purpose, without financial, legal, or technical barriers other than those inseparable from gaining access to the internet itself” ([Budapest Open Access Initiative, 2002](#)).

Gold Open Access: Where a published output is immediately openly accessible upon publication via a journal website.

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Green Open Access: Where a published is openly accessible from a public repository.

Hybrid Journal: Subscription journals that charge an extra fee to make a specific article open access while the remainder of the journal remains behind a paywall.

Transitional Agreement: Contracts which gradually shift the basis of payments from an institution to a publisher from subscription-based reading to open access publishing services in a controlled manner.

CRedit: The Contributor Roles Taxonomy is a high-level taxonomy used to indicate the roles typically adopted by contributors to scholarly output.

Preprint: A publicly available version of any type of scientific manuscript/research output preceding formal publication, considered a form of Green Open Access.

Open peer review: A scholarly review mechanism providing disclosure of any combination of author and referee identities, as well as peer-review reports and editorial decision letters, to one another or publicly at any point during or after the peer review or publication process. It may also refer to the removal of restrictions on who can participate in peer review and the platforms for doing so. Note that ‘open peer review’ has been used interchangeably to refer to any, or all, of the above practices.

Research Culture: The behaviours, values, expectations, attitudes and norms of research communities.

Version Control

Version Control	Revision Date	Summary of Changes
1	July 2023	New policy created which incorporates several previous policies relating to research.
2	September 2025	Minor additions; reference to a new standalone policy on Software Development and Training of AI Algorithms.

